

Spatial and Kinematic Properties for a Simulated Population of Runaway Stars

Tai Boon, Ding¹

Harvard College, Department of Astronomy

Abstract

Runaway stars found in the halo of the Milky Way begin their trajectories in the galactic disk and are ejected either through dynamic interactions or supernova events. To predict the spatial and kinematic properties of runaways, we launch 1200000 stars of 6 different masses, half originating from the dynamical ejection scenario and half from supernovae ejection, into a Galactic potential and compute their trajectories through the Galaxy. Across the masses, the resulting runaway populations have flattened spatial distributions, with higher velocity stars especially concentrated in the galactic disk. Stars ejected by the two different mechanisms display different final spatial and kinematic properties, hence the overall properties of the population depend on the relative occurrences of these mechanisms. This presents a possible method to study the relative contributions of the mechanisms in future studies.

Introduction

Runaway stars are stars that are observed at great distances relative to where they were formed, typically with large rest-frame velocities. Runaway stars are formed in the Milky Way disk and ejected into high-velocity orbits. Since their discovery by Humason & Zwicky in 1947, two primary mechanisms have been identified for the ejections of these stars. In the dynamical ejection scenario (DE), runaways are produced as the result of strong gravitational interactions between systems of multiple stars, which then sling one or some of the members outwards (Poveda, Ruiz, & Allen 1967); in the supernova ejection scenario (SNE), the more massive member of a stellar binary explodes as a supernova and unbinds the binary, subsequently causing its companion to be ejected (Blaauw 1961).

Observations made using Hipparcos data have traced the origins of runaway stars to both supernova events and stellar cluster ejections (Hoogerwerf et al. 2001). Hence the current consensus is that both mechanisms produce runaway stars, though there is no consensus on the relative contributions of DE versus SNE. Gies & Bolton argued that the low binary frequency of runaways should favor DE (1986); however, it is also possible that SNE can give high enough kick velocities such that unpaired ejections may occur (Murphy et al. 2004). Intuitively, since the cross-section of dynamic encounters is higher for more

¹ The author would like to express his gratitude to Dr. Warren Brown from the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics for providing the numerical scheme used for the simulations in this paper, and also for his mentorship throughout the research process.

massive stars due to gravitational focusing, we should expect DE to account for a greater proportion of massive runaway stars. To this end, Zwart (2000) proposed that at most 30% of runaway O stars are ejected via SNE, while runaway B stars are almost all ejected via SNE. Focusing on the DE mechanism, Perets & Subr (2012) also concluded that the DE runaway fraction of O stars is two to three times that of B stars.

One possible approach to formulate the relative contributions of the DE and SNE mechanisms is to consider the use of Monte-Carlo simulations to make assays of the spatial and kinematic distribution of runaway stars throughout the galaxy. Stars ejected by SNE are ejected close to the start of their lifetimes when their much more massive companions ($> 10 M_{\text{sun}}$) companions (with far shorter lifetimes) explode in a supernova event; in comparison, stars ejected by DE can be ejected at any point during their lifetimes. Consequently, for a given mass stars ejected by SNE spend on average a greater fraction of their main-sequence lifetimes as runaways compared to stars ejected by DE, and hence simulations using different ratios of ejection scenarios should produce different final spatial and kinematic distributions. Combined with further understanding about the fraction of all stars that are ejected as runaways, it may be possible to compare simulated catalogs with results from existing radial velocities surveys.²

In recent years, several studies have derived simulated catalogs for runaway stars based on specific ejection conditions. Bromley et al. (2009) simulated a population of runaway stars being injected into a Galactic potential and traced their orbits through the Galaxy. For observational purposes it was useful to focus specifically on runaways that reach the halo, for it is at the halo where the signatures of a runaway star may be most easily distinguished against the population of background stars. For the initial distribution of ejection velocities, results from published analyses of stars ejected via SNE were used, due to a lack of similar results for DE. Perets and Subr (2012) later filled in this gap by making use of N-body simulations of massive clusters to characterize the expected ejection velocity distribution for the DE process. The velocity distribution was found to follow a broken power law, with high-velocity ejections far less common than low-velocity ejections.

Here we build on the work of Bromley et al. (2009) by simulating the orbits of stars that have been ejected from the disk by both DE and SNE, in a 50-50 ratio. Like Bromley et al., we have chosen to focus on intermediate mass $1.5 - 6 M_{\text{sun}}$ runaway stars, for the same reason that we are most interested in observing stars that reach the halo. More massive ($> 6 M_{\text{sun}}$) stars are not considered because their lifetimes are too short to reach large distances in the halo, while stars with mass ($< 1.5 M_{\text{sun}}$) are too faint to observe in the halo. The lifetimes of intermediate mass stars range from $10^8 - 10^9$ years; hence they have only been formed recently in the disk. With our model, we first derived the spatial and velocity distributions of runaways as a function of mass, and then proceeded

² In particular, the GAIA mission (to be launched in December 2013) will measure the positions, distances and proper motions of stars up to an accuracy of $200 \mu\text{m}$ for $m = 20$ mag stars (which translates into a distance limit of ~ 25 kpc for a $1.5 M_{\text{sun}}$). With such surveys, velocity outliers in the solar neighborhood and around the North Galactic Pole may thus be readily identified.

to conduct a magnitude-limited observation of the North Galactic pole ($60^\circ \leq b \leq 90^\circ$) to determine the frequency of different mass runways that would be observed in this region and establish the range of proper motions that would be associated with these runaways. Finally, we also conducted observations in regions within 1 kpc of the Sun facing perpendicular to the direction of the galactic center ($80^\circ \leq l \leq 100^\circ$), to uncover signatures of possible runaway candidates in our immediate neighborhood.

Methods

The model we used to derive the global spatial and velocity distribution of runaways in the Milky Way is similar to that used by Bromley et al., which uses the Galactic potential model defined by Kenyon et al. (2008) to model the distribution of mass in the galaxy. This disk, bulge, and halo model fits observations of the Galaxy on scales from 5 pc to 100 kpc and has a circular orbital velocities of 220 km s^{-1} at $r = 8 \text{ kpc}$. We then consider runaways ejected from an exponential disk with a distribution of initial velocities representative of the respective ejection mechanisms (DE and SNE). At the end of the simulations, the results are transformed from a galactocentric Cartesian coordinate system to galactic coordinates centered at the Sun (b, l , along with other information such as distance, radial and rest-frame velocities), so that the resulting distributions can be studied by latitude and longitude cuts.

To set up the initial positions of the runaway stars, we adopted the same exponential disk profile as Bromley et al., which describes the distribution of initial radius by the probability distribution function:

$$P(r) \propto r * e^{(-r/2.4 \text{ kpc})}$$

where 2.4 is the radial scale length of the disk (Sigel et al. 2002). A lower limit of 3 kpc was set since runaways ejected from $r < 3 \text{ kpc}$ are unlikely to reach the halo, while a cutoff of 30 kpc was set as the upper limit of initial radius, the edge of the observed stellar disk (Bromley et al. 2009). With initial radius drawn randomly from the distribution above, initial height in the thin disk was drawn uniformly between $[-0.15, 0.15]^3$. Figure 1 below displays the sample of initial radii and Figure 2 displays the exponential profile of the runaway stars before being set into orbit.

³ The density of stars in the thin disk also follows an exponential profile in the vertical direction, but since the radial scale is much larger than the vertical scale, we assume a uniform vertical distribution here for simplicity.

Fig. 1: Probability distribution for initial radii (left) and simulated distribution of initial radii (right)

Fig. 2: Initial positions of runaway stars

To assign initial velocities to the runaway stars, we made use of different function for DE and SNE mechanisms. For DE, Perets and Subr (2012) found the velocity distribution to follow a broken power law:

$$P(v) \propto v^{-8/3} \text{ for } v \leq 150 \text{ kms}^{-1}, \text{ and}$$

$$P(v) \propto v^{-3/2} \text{ for } v > 150 \text{ kms}^{-1}$$

For SNE, we used the probability distribution function used by Bromley et al.:

$$P(v) \propto e^{-v/150 \text{ km/s}}$$

which is an approximation to the Portegies Zwart simulation of binary supernova ejections. As before, we set arbitrary limits of $[20 \text{ km/s}^{-1}, 400 \text{ km/s}^{-1}]$ for the ejection velocities, since stars ejected at $v < 20 \text{ km/s}^{-1}$ are unlikely to make it to the halo and stars ejected at $v > 400 \text{ km/s}^{-1}$ are too increasingly rare to affect our simulations significantly. Figure 3 displays the sample of initial ejection velocities drawn from the respective distributions. With these ejection velocities, the initial trajectories are then calculated by drawing directions randomly from a uniform distribution, assuming that there is no preferred direction for ejection.

Fig. 3: Probability distribution for initial velocities for SNE (top left), simulated distribution of ejection velocities for SNE (top right); probability distribution for initial velocities for DE (bottom left), simulated distribution of ejection velocities for DE (bottom right);

To follow the trajectories of ejected stars, we integrate the equations of motion numerically using the fourth-order Burlirsh-Stoer method. Assuming the same starting point in time for all the stars, the orbits for stars ejected for DE are integrated for a random time t , where t lies between 0 and the main sequence lifetime of the runaway star.

Mass (Msun)	Main sequence lifetime (Myr)
1.5	2900
2	1200
3	360
4	160
5	95
6	65

Table 4: Lifetimes of stars in our simulation

For stars ejected via SNE, the supernovae caused by their more massive binary companions happens relatively near the start of their lifetimes; furthermore, the pre-supernova binary goes through a phase of mass transfer from the more massive star to the less massive star, which rejuvenates the less massive stars in the process (Zwart 2000). Therefore in our simulation we assume for simplicity that SNE runaways have ages of zero when they are ejected, and the orbits for these stars are integrated over their entire main sequence lifetimes (Table 4).

Finally, we conduct magnitude-limited observations of the simulated runaways from an assumed solar position of $(x, y, z) = (-8, 0, 0)$ kpc. For populations of runaway stars of particular interest, their galactic coordinates and tangential velocities are further converted to equatorial coordinates and proper motion for future comparisons against star catalogs.

Results of Simulations

At the end of the simulations, the final spatial distributions for all 6 masses of runaway stars are displayed in Figure 5. Across all 6 masses, we see that the original thin disk has “puffed” up, with larger radial and vertical scales compared to the main stellar disk. Even so, the majority of runaways remain bounded, which suggests that galactic potential plays an important role in determining the spatial properties of runaway stars. Furthermore, since higher mass stars spend less time in orbit, the number of runaways that make it to great distances in the halo decreases with mass.

Fig. 5: Final positions of runaway stars (1.5 – 6 Msun)

Figure 6 displays the cumulative frequency of runaway stars by galactic latitude; Figure 7 takes $|b|$ and plots the $\log(\text{frequency})$ of runaways of each mass in 6 evenly spaced latitude bins from $|b| = 0^\circ$ to $|b| = 90^\circ$. From both figures, we can see that more than 80% of all runaways (across all masses) remain at low latitudes $0^\circ \leq |b| \leq 30^\circ$. However, as Figure 8 shows, the fraction of runaways that are at low attitudes increases by mass, which is what we would expect. Similarly, Figure 9 calculates the proportion of runaways of each mass that end up at $|b| \geq 45^\circ$ and we clearly observe a decreasing trend by mass.

Fig. 6: Cumulative frequency plot of latitudes

Fig. 7: Log(frequency) plot of absolute latitudes (separated into 6 bins)

Mass (Msun)	$0^\circ < b \leq 15^\circ$ (Fraction)	$15^\circ < b \leq 30^\circ$ (Fraction)	$30^\circ < b \leq 45^\circ$ (Fraction)	$45^\circ < b \leq 60^\circ$ (Fraction)	$60^\circ < b \leq 75^\circ$ (Fraction)	$75^\circ < b \leq 90^\circ$ (Fraction)
1.5	0.829	0.109	0.0378	0.0161	0.00630	0.00188
2	0.840	0.102	0.0359	0.0152	0.00597	0.00169
3	0.852	0.0934	0.0322	0.0143	0.00598	0.00183
4	0.858	0.0836	0.0370	0.0369	0.00561	0.00159
5	0.0861	0.0856	0.0317	0.0135	0.00619	0.00185
6	0.872	0.0835	0.0282	0.0115	0.00408	0.00095

Table 8: Fraction of stars in each $|b|$ bin

Fig. 9: Fraction of stars with $|b| \geq 45^\circ$, by mass

Besides comparing between masses, we were also interested in comparing between the DE and SNE mechanisms. Due to shorter times spent in orbit (on average), DE runaways are more likely to be found at lower latitudes across all 6 masses (Figure 11). For a 50-50 ratio of DE and SNE runaways, Table 10 shows the differences in the mean and median latitudes of the runaways.⁴

Mass (Msun)	Mean latitude (SNE) – Mean latitude (DE)	Median latitude (SNE) – Median latitude (DE)
1.5	2.81	1.44
2	2.90	1.40
3	3.27	1.54
4	4.20	1.70
5	4.88	1.68
6	4.81	1.76

Table 10: SNE versus DE, latitude comparisons

⁴ Although we did not explore different ratios of SNE and DE runaways in this paper, we hypothesize that the magnitudes of these differences would likely depend on the ratio used in a given simulation

Fig. 11: Cumulative frequency plots of latitudes, SNE versus DE

Figure 12 shows a cumulative frequency plot of the final velocities of the runaways. Compared to the initial ejection velocities, there is an overall shift of the curve towards higher velocities, caused by the initial velocity boost from galactic rotation.

Fig. 12: Cumulative frequency plot of runaway stars, by mass and velocities

It is interesting to note that there are runaway stars of all 6 masses that remain within the high velocity regime at the end of the simulations, with almost 20% of all stars having final velocities $v > 300 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. For the sake of observation, we are most interested in these extreme outliers; unfortunately, these high-velocity runaways are also preferentially found in the disk, along the direction of galactic rotation. In fact, comparing Figure 13

(cumulative frequency plot of galactic latitude for high-velocity runaways) with Figure 6, the slope from $-20^\circ \leq b \leq 20^\circ$ is much steeper, indicating that the fraction of high-velocity runaways trapped at low latitudes is larger than the fraction for of the overall population. Nevertheless high-velocity runaways do exist at all latitudes, and our goal in the next section is to find the ones that are located at spatial positions which lend themselves most conveniently to Earth-based observations.

Fig. 13: Cumulative frequency plots of latitudes for runaways with $v \geq 300 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Observations and Discussion

After concatenating data from the full suite of simulations, we proceeded to conduct an Earth-based, magnitude-limited survey of the runaway population. The purpose of such a survey is to predict the number of runaways we would expect to find in some given region of the sky, though another approach (not performed here) that could have been taken is to observe numerous patches of the sky (save for directly into the Galactic plane) to report a region where the probability of finding candidate runaway stars is the highest.

Based on the observation footprint of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey, we decided to focus our first set of observations on the North Galactic Pole. This translates to an observational cut of latitude $b \geq 30^\circ$, and we impose a detection limit of 20 mag (both Sloan and GAIA have a similar limit). For our population of simulated runaway, this magnitude limit only affects the 1.5 – 3 Msun stars, where a few outliers do lie further than the maximum distance where they can be detected.

As pointed out earlier, the signatures of runaway stars would be more distinguishable at high latitudes than in the galactic disk, if nothing else simply because there are less background stars. Furthermore, normal 5 – 6 Msun stars do not usually live long enough

to migrate that far outwards from where they are formed in the disk, therefore making a high latitude survey an ideal starting point to hunt for candidate runaway stars.

Table 15 below shows the runaway stars remaining after applying a latitude cut at $b \geq 30^\circ$, a velocity cut of $v \geq 300 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and magnitude cuts specific to each mass. Out of the original population, the fraction of each mass type that qualified under the latitude cut is presented in the second column of Table 15. The fourth column gives the numbers of each mass type that qualified after velocity and magnitude cuts have been further applied.

Mass (Msun)	Absolute magnitude ⁵	Observational Limit at $m = 20$ (kpc)
1.5	3	25.1
2	1.95	40.7
3	0.65	74.3
4	- 0.25	112
5	- 0.6	132
6	- 1.2	174

Table 14: Observation limits for different masses

Mass (Msun)	Fraction at $30^\circ \leq b \leq 90^\circ$	Ratio of $V_b > 0$ to $V_b < 0$	Number of observable Stars with $v > 300 \text{ km s}^{-1}$
1.5	0.0310	1.01	161
2	0.0293	1.02	129
3	0.0270	0.98	147
4	0.0291	1.17	97
5	0.0271	1.13	146
6	0.0221	1.50	138

Table 15: Observation star fraction at $30^\circ \leq b \leq 90^\circ$, ratio of outward moving to inward moving stars and stars counts

Fig. 16: Observed stars, $30^\circ \leq b \leq 90^\circ$

⁵ Allen's astrophysical quantities, 4th ed. Publisher: New York: AIP Press; Springer, 2000. Edited by Arthur N. Cox.

In the third column of Table 15, we calculated the ratio of stars that were traveling farther out from the disk to the ones that were moving downwards for each of the 6 masses. While the lower mass stars spend a longer proportion of their lifetimes as runaways, they usually travel to a maximum radius before falling back into the disk; hence for the 1.5 - 3 Msun stars this ratio is close to unity. In contrast, the higher mass runaways have a higher ratio of outward moving stars to inward moving stars, since a larger fraction of the runaways is still making the first orbit outwards.

For our observation of runaways at the NGP, the range of proper motions (in mas/year) is [0.0004999, 0.1459]. While this range of proper motions is technically within GAIA's limits, we can reduce the inaccuracy of our proper motion measurements by searching for runaways nearer to the Sun.

Keeping in mind the zone of avoidance, we make a second observation based on a longitude cut of $80^\circ \leq l \leq 100^\circ$ (Figure 17) within the solar neighborhood (1 kpc radius). Since these stars are much closer to us, we lowered the velocity cut-off to 100 km s^{-1} and found a total of 43 runaway stars. Of these, 15 are moving inwards of the solar circle and 28 are moving outwards, a ratio consistent with the initial spatial profile of the runaways (the exponential disk). The stars in this sample have a range of proper motions of [0.136, 0.165], which is slightly larger than those from the NGP sample. They also have a velocity dispersion of 46.9 km s^{-1} , about 4 times larger than the typical velocity dispersion for stars in the solar neighborhood.

Fig. 17: Observed stars, $80^\circ \leq l \leq 100^\circ$

Mass (Msun)	Number of runaway stars at $80^\circ \leq l \leq 100^\circ$
1.5	7
2	4
3	10
4	6
5	7
6	9

Table 18: Observed star counts, by mass ($80^\circ \leq l \leq 100^\circ$)

So then the question arises: can we use our simulations to predict the number of runaway stars we might expect to find near the NGP or within $80^\circ \leq l \leq 100^\circ$ of the solar neighborhood? The answer to that depends on several factors. We must exercise caution in extrapolating from this set of simulations, as much is yet unknown about the actual formation rates of runaway stars. Stone (1991) estimated that $\sim 2.5\%$ of B stars and $\sim 0.3\%$ of A stars are runaways, and lower mass stars will not be ejected as runaways at all. While this is not the final word on the matter, we can apply these estimates to our simulations of 2 – 6 Msun runaways to gain a sense of how populous these stars would be in our observation regions. If $\sim 0.13\%$ and $\sim 0.6\%$ of stars in the Galaxy are B and A stars respectively, and assuming a star formation rate of 1 Msun/year, we can expect to find ~ 7000 B-type runaways and ~ 3000 A-type runaways around the NGP, and ~ 400 B-type runaways and ~ 180 A-type runaways with 1 kpc of $80^\circ \leq l \leq 100^\circ$.

Conclusion

In this study, we simulated the trajectories of 1200000 stars that have been ejected from the Galactic disk randomly. We find that while final spatial and kinematic properties are affected by varying stellar lifetimes (mass), in general the spatial kinematic distributions across all masses follow the same trends. The spatial profile of runaways, while more extended than the original thin disk, is essentially flat. Some 90% of all runaways are confined within $|b| \leq 20^\circ$, though a slightly larger fraction of low-mass runaways made it to higher latitudes. The final velocity profile of the runaways indicated that almost 20% achieve rest-frame velocities greater than 300 kms^{-1} regardless of their mass-type, but some 99% of these high-velocity runaways are confined within $|b| \leq 20^\circ$.

For the small group of runaways that do travel all the way to the halo after being ejected from the galactic disk, the deviation of their trajectory from the Galactic center is related to the dark matter distribution in the Galaxy. Therefore a better understanding of where runaways can be found and how they came to be where they are may reveal insights into the dark matter distribution in the Galaxy.

Furthermore, we used a 50-50 ratio of ejections via DE and ejections via SNE for our stars, which, in terms of simulation parameters, translated into different distributions of ejection velocities and the average time that stars of each mass-type spent as runaways. As noted, this gave rise to observable differences in the spatial

and kinematic properties of the runaways of both types; hence suggesting the part that ejection mechanism has to play in determining the overall properties of the population. An obvious extension to this study would be to vary the ratios of DE and SNE ejections to explore how the final spatial and kinematic properties would change accordingly, and possibly use data from future radial velocity to determine the relative contributions of each mechanism.

Finally, we conducted magnitude-limited observations of our simulated runaways, first with a latitude cut of $b \geq 30^\circ$ and then around part of the solar neighborhood. In these surveys, we find that only a very small fraction of all runaways are actually *observable* from our position on Earth. Of the runaways we observed around the NGP, the ratio of runaways moving away from and towards the galactic disk is close to unity for the 1.5 – 3 Msun runaways, while for the 4 – 6 Msun runaways the outwards moving stars outnumber inward moving stars by 17% - 50%. For our solar neighborhood observation, the number of stars moving into the solar circle is roughly half the number of those moving outwards. Around the NGP, we calculated the proper motions to be between [0.0004999, 0.1459] mas/year; for $80^\circ \leq l \leq 100^\circ$ in the solar neighborhood we calculated proper motions of [0.136, 0.165] mas/year. Using larger scale simulations and/or multiple observations from different points on the solar circle in our simulation, we believe that these figures can be improved further.

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